

CREEP AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF HYBRID REINFORCED MAGNESIUM ALLOY AE42

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SUMMARY: Magnesium alloys have gained increasing interest especially in automotive application due to the alloys low density. Weight saving plays an important role when green house gases should be reduced. One obstacle is the poor creep resistance of magnesium alloys at elevated temperatures. Alloy development as well as development of magnesium based metal matrix composites are possible solutions. In this paper, hybrid reinforced composites based on magnesium alloy AE42 produced by squeeze casting are investigated. Compression creep properties at different loads and temperatures are investigated as well as microstructural changes during creep by optical microscopy.

KEYWORDS: MMC, hybrid, particle, fibre, magnesium, squeeze casting, creep, threshold stress.

INTRODUCTION

During the 1930's and 40's there was a rapid increase in the use of magnesium alloys in transportation technologies. Magnesium alloy gearbox housings and engine blocks were produced by chill casting, as a result of the relatively low engine temperatures the alloys proved adequate. Development of modern water-cooled engines increased the application temperature and magnesium alloys were replaced by gray cast iron and aluminium because of the limited strength and creep resistance of magnesium alloys at higher temperatures. At the end of the last century alloy development as well as development of magnesium based metal matrix composites (MMCs) was carried out to improve the high temperature strength and creep resistance. Alloy development occurred in several directions; either the reduction of aluminum and the addition of elements that preferentially combine with aluminum or the complete elimination of aluminum as an addition. The need to eliminate or reduce the aluminum content is because it is known that β phase ($Mg_{17}Al_{12}$) contributes to the poor creep resistance in aluminum containing alloys. From the aluminum containing magnesium high-pressure-die-casting (HPDC) alloys, AE42 currently shows best creep properties. This is due to the Al-RE precipitates, which suppress the formation of $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$. In the field of magnesium based MMCs many developments in processing and reinforcement have taken place in the last 25 years. Particle reinforced magnesium based MMCs with SiC, BN or TiB produced by powder metallurgy or stir casting were investigated [1-4] as well as short [5-9] or long fiber [10, 11] reinforced MMCs, where alumina or carbon fibers reinforce the magnesium alloy. A combination of both particles and short fibers, known as hybrid reinforcement, is used in this investigation. The advantage of higher amount of particles is on the one hand reduction of mechanical anisotropy, that occurs in fiber reinforced MMCs due to not randomly distributed fibers and on the other hand reduced costs. Preforms with different amounts of alumina (Saffil[®])-fibers and SiC-particles were infiltrated with AE42 magnesium

alloy melt using the squeeze-cast process. Solidification under pressure reduces porosity compared to die castings.

MANUFACTURE OF THE HYBRID COMPOSITES

The hybrid preforms were made up of different amounts of alumina (Saffil[®])- fibers and SiC-particles. Whereas the SiC particles show a random distribution due to their shape, the fibres in the preform have a planar isotropic distribution. Table 1 shows composition of the hybrid and short fibre preforms. Fibers have a length and a diameter of about 180 μm , 8 μm respectively, and particles have a diameter up to 30 μm . Fibres and particles are stuck together by 4 wt.% silica based binder. The creep behaviour of the hybrid composites was compared to the creep behaviour of short fibre reinforced AE42 with an amount of 20 vol% Saffil[®]-fibres. Monolithic alloy AE42 (aluminum and rare earths) was used as matrix alloy. Table 2 shows the chemical composition of the alloy AE42 used in this investigation.

Table 1: Amount of reinforcement in the preforms

Preform	Alumina (Saffil [®]) fiber [vol%]	SiC particles [vol%]
10/10	10	10
10/15	10	15
15/5	15	5
20/0	20	0

Table 2: Composition of magnesium alloy AE42

Element	Al	Zn	Mn	Si	Ce	La	Nd	Pr	Th	Mg
wt.%	3,9	<0,01	0,3	0,01	1,2	0,6	0,4	0,1	0,2	remainder

Hybrid and short fiber reinforced magnesium composites were manufactured at the EMPA (Eidgenössische Materialprüfungs- und Forschungsanstalt) in Thun/Switzerland. The squeeze casting process was used for infiltration of the pre-manufactured preforms [12-14]. Squeeze casting is the most common casting process for the manufacture of MMCs. Fig. 1 shows a sketch of a squeeze cast tool.

Fig.1: Sketch of a squeeze cast tool

After preheating the preform up to 750°C in order to burn the organic binder and to stabilize the inorganic binder the preform is put into the die. The die has a temperature of 300°C at its

sides and 150°C at the bottom. The superheated alloy with a temperature of 770°C is poured manually over the preform and the upper ram squeezes the melt into the preform with a speed of 10 mm/s. The part solidifies under a pressure of 100 MPa in about 20 s. This process is called direct squeeze casting, because the melt is squeezed directly with the upper ram. There is no gate system, so the amount of melt influences directly the size of the part. Cylindrical specimens with a length of 15 mm and a diameter of 6 mm were prepared by spark erosion. All samples were with their length taken out of the fibre plane.

CREEP INVESTIGATIONS

Creep tests were conducted in compression because this mode is closer to the real situation when for example partial reinforcements in engine blocks or gear box housings at the area of bolts are considered, it is always a compressive load that they are exposed to. Advantages of compressive creep tests are to found in the specimen preparation, small cylinders are easier to produce, specimens can fail only in their gauge length and not outside (which is not possible with tension specimens). Another advantage, especially for MMCs is the small size of the cylinders required. This allows for specimens to be taken out of small areas in different directions.

Creep tests were conducted in lever arm creep test machines from ATM. Tests at constant temperatures (200°C, 240°C and 270°C) and constant loads (100 MPa, 120 MPa and 140 MPa) were performed until the minimum creep rate was reached. As an example, creep curves of tests performed at 270°C and 140 MPa load are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Creep curves from tests performed at 270°C and 140 MPa

In order to calculate stress exponent n from power-law-equation (Eqn. 1)

$$\dot{\epsilon}_s = A_0 \sigma^n \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_s$ is the minimum or secondary creep rate, A_0 is a constant factor and σ is the applied stress, the slopes of plots of $\log \dot{\epsilon}_s$ against $\log \sigma$ have to be evaluated. Fig. 3, 4 and 5 show these plots at 200°C, 240°C and 270°C respectively. Values at the lines indicate the stress exponent n . At all temperatures hybrid composite reinforced with 15 vol% Saffil[®] and 5 vol%

SiC-particles show slightly reduced creep resistance compared to the other MMCs. Table 3 shows values of stress exponent n .

Table 3: Stress exponent values

MMC	200°C	240°C	270°C
AE42 + 10/10	6.6	9	13.7
AE42 + 10/15	5.0	12.2	18.4
AE42 + 15/5	10.7	10.8	13.1
AE42 + 20/0	6.2	10	16

Fig. 3: Minimum creep rate against creep stress of composites at 200°C

Fig. 4: Minimum creep rate against creep stress of composites at 240°C

Fig. 5: Minimum creep rate against creep stress of composites at 270°C

The stress exponent n of metallic materials is connected to the predominate deformation mechanisms during the creep experiments. When $n=1$, deformation is connected to diffusion controlled mechanisms like Nabarro-Herring- or Coble-creep, $n=3$ or $n=5$ means that dislocation motion is the predominant mechanism. At high temperatures and stresses a power-law-breakdown takes place. High values of n , as seen here have not been connected to mechanisms directly, however such high values are commonly reported for MMCs [15-17].

In order to explain these values for MMCs a threshold stress σ_0 was introduced, which is defined as a lower stress limit, below no strain is measurable in creep tests. It occurs due to internal stresses because of the high number of interfaces. Steady state creep rate is than a function of $(\sigma - \sigma_0)$ as it is shown in Eqn. 2.

$$\dot{\epsilon}_s = \frac{ADGb}{kT} \left(\frac{\sigma - \sigma_0}{G} \right)^n \quad (2)$$

Where D is the diffusion coefficient, b the Burgers vector, k is Boltzmann constant and G is the shear modulus. Li and Langdon [18] present a simple procedure for calculating the threshold stress. An extrapolation of $\log \dot{\epsilon}_s$ against $\log \sigma$ -plots to a creep rate of $1 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{s}^{-1}$, which is in the area of the lowest measurable strain, is expected to bring the threshold stress for each temperature. After threshold stress extrapolation, plots of $\log \dot{\epsilon}_s$ against the effective creep stress were carried out and are shown in Fig. 6, 7 and 8. Values of true stress exponent are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Values of true stress exponent

MMC	200°C	240°C	270°C
AE42 + 10/10	3.1	4.6	6.1
AE42 + 10/15	2.9	4.1	5.9
AE42 + 15/5	3.2	5.5	6.9
AE42 + 20/0	3.2	4.6	6.5

Fig. 6: Minimum creep rate against effective creep stress of composites at 200°C

Fig. 7: Minimum creep rate against effective creep stress of composites at 240°C

At 200°C, true stress exponents between 2.9 and 3.2 are calculated, at 240°C it is already between 4.1 and 5.5. At 270°C true stress exponent is between 5.9 and 6.9. The increase in the true stress exponent with temperature is strongly connected with changes in deformation mechanism during creep. It is well known, that the hcp magnesium alloys change their deformation behaviour above 220°C due to newly activated slip systems (primarily pyramidal slip). This effect and an increase of not only sliding but also dislocation climb is likely to result in the increase in the true stress exponent.

Fig. 8: Minimum creep rate against effective creep stress of composites at 270°C

MICROSTRUCTURAL INVESTIGATIONS

Optical microscopy was performed on specimens before and after creep. After grinding and polishing test samples were etched with picric acid. In Fig. 9 a hybrid composite with 10 vol% Saffil® fibers and 10 vol% SiC-particles is shown in the as cast state. Particles as well as fibers are distributed randomly in the matrix, and grains of the AE42 matrix alloy are visible. They show a grain size of about 100µm. In Fig. 10 the same material is shown after creep. A significant decrease of the grain size is visible. It can be due to dynamic recrystallisation processes or subgrain formation during mechanical creep deformation.

Fig. 9: Micrograph of a 10vol% Saffil® + 10vol% SiC_p MMC in the as cast state

Fig. 10: Micrograph of a 10vol% Saffil[®] + 10vol% SiC_p MMC after creep

CONCLUSIONS

Magnesium based hybrid composites reinforced with different amounts of Saffil[®] fibers and SiC-particles were produced by direct Squeeze casting. In compression creep tests the material was investigated and compared to a short fibre reinforced MMC with the same matrix alloy AE42. It could be shown, that composites reinforced with 15 vol% Saffil[®] fibers and 5 vol% SiC-particles have slightly worse creep properties compared to the other MMCs. Microstructural investigation performed with optical microscopy shows a significant decrease in grain size during the creep experiments.

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